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Cyberbullying in High School and University Students: The Roles of Gender, Age and Internet Spending Time

Lise ve Üniversite Öğrencilerinde Siber Zorbalık: Cinsiyet, Yaş ve İnternet Kalma Süresinin Rollerini

ABSTRACT

Although the use of Information and Communication Technologies in education has many positive effects, it has also brought about global problems such as cyberbullying. This study was designed to determine the situation of cyberbullying, which has increased due to its widespread use due to current needs, in a small city located in Central Western Anatolia, Turkey, after the COVID-19 pandemic. While high school and university students were included in the study and the age factor was evaluated, gender and internet spending time were also evaluated. The data of 111 female and 89 male (n: 200) volunteer students were included in the study. 68 (34%) of the students were from high school and 132 (66%) from university. The 'Cyberbullying Scale' was used in the study. 53.5% (n = 107) of all participants reported that they were subjected to cyberbullying, while 34.5% (n = 69) reported that they were bullied. The results of the studies revealed that male students have a higher tendency to engage in cyberbullying, that male students are exposed to cyberbullying at the same rate as female students, that high school students are exposed to cyberbullying at a similar rate to university students, that students spend approximately one-third of their waking hours in the virtual environment, and that male students and high school students are exposed to cyberbullying more frequently.

Keywords: Cyberbullying, Gender, High School Students, University Students

ÖZET

Bilgi ve İletişim Teknolojilerinin eğitimde kullanılması birçok olumlu etkiye sahip olmakla birlikte siber zorbalık gibi küresel sorunları da beraberinde getirmiştir. Bu çalışma, güncel ihtiyaçlar nedeniyle yaygın kullanımı artan siber zorbalığın, COVID-19 pandemisinden sonra Türkiye'nin Orta Batı Anadolu Bölgesi'nde bulunan küçük bir şehirdeki durumunu belirlemek amacıyla tasarlanmıştır. Çalışmaya lise ve üniversite öğrencileri dahil edilerek yaş faktörü değerlendirilirken, cinsiyet ve internette kalma süresi de değerlendirilmiştir. Çalışmaya 111 kadın ve 89 erkek (n: 200) gönüllü öğrencinin verileri dahil edilmiştir. Öğrencilerin 68'i (%34) lise ve 132'si (%66) üniversite mezunudur. Çalışmada 'Siber Zorbalık Ölçeği' kullanılmıştır. Tüm katılımcıların %53,5'i (n=107) siber zorbalığa maruz kaldığını, %34,5'i (n=69) ise zorbalığa uğradığını bildirmiştir. Çalışma sonuçları, erkek öğrencilerin siber zorbalığa katılma eğilimlerinin daha yüksek olduğunu, erkek öğrencilerin kız öğrencilerle aynı oranda siber zorbalığa maruz kaldığını, lise öğrencilerinin üniversite öğrencileriyle benzer oranda siber zorbalığa maruz kaldığını, öğrencilerin uyanık oldukları saatlerin yaklaşık üçte birini sanal ortamda geçirdiklerini ve erkek öğrenciler ile lise öğrencilerinin siber zorbalığa daha sık maruz kaldıklarını ortaya koymuştur.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Siberzorbalık, Cinsiyet, Lise Öğrencileri, Üniversite Öğrencileri

1. INTRODUCTION

The fact that individuals of all ages can easily access rapid developments in the field of Information and Communication Technologies has made it an indispensable part of life. Although the use of Information and Communication Technologies in education has many positive effects, it has also brought new problems. One of these problems is bullying. These bullying activities that occur with the misuse of Information and Communication Technologies are called cyberbullying, electronic bullying or online bullying. When the common aspects of the definitions in the literature are combined, cyberbullying can be defined as any behavior that is carried out by individuals or groups via electronic or digital media and repeatedly transmits hostile or aggressive messages that are intended to harm or disturb others (Tokunaga, 2010). Cyberbullying is seen to be implemented in different ways: sending angry, rude and insulting messages, sending humiliating messages, sharing information without permission in the virtual environment, sharing private or humiliating information or photos of people in the electronic environment, online fights, constant and intense harassment or critical traumatization and slander, imitation, deliberate and brutal exclusion of a person from an online group or environment, virtual threats (Vogels, 2022; Teng et al, 2024).

Cyberbullying is a global problem. It is difficult to obtain the percentages of cyber victimization and cyberbullying globally due to differences in research methods, demographic characteristics and measurement. Although it is difficult to determine its prevalence, a recent study reported that 13% to 57% of children and adolescents are victims of cyberbullying and 6% to 46% of them have committed cyberbullying acts. (Zhu et al, 2021). Global average perpetration rates have been reported to be approximately 25% and victimization to be 33% according to studies conducted between 2015 and 2019 (Zhu et al, 2021). Some of the highest cyber victimization rates are 57% in Spain (Marco and Tormo-Irun, 2018), 52% in Malaysia (Marret and Choo, 2017), and 44% in China (Rao et al, 2019). Canada and South Korea have been reported to have low victimization rates of 13% and 14%, respectively, and perpetration rates of 7% and 6% (Beran et al, 2015; Lee and Shin, 2017). As in the world, cyberbullying incidents have increased rapidly in Turkey in recent years. When studies conducted on high school and university students in Turkey between 2007 and 2012 are examined, it is seen that exposure to cyberbullying varies between 23% and 48%, and the rate of cyberbullying varies between 30% and 55% (Erdur Baker and Kavsut, 2007; Aricak et al, 2008, Topçu and Erdur Baker, 2010; Dilmaç 2009; Peker et al, 2012). In 2017, Ulasdemir and Kucuk showed that exposure to cyberbullying increased to 65.5% and cyberbullying increased to 56.6% among adolescents (Uludasdemir and Kucuk, 2019).

When the studies conducted in Turkey are examined, it is seen that the majority of them belong to the period before the COVID-19 pandemic. The national quarantines and widespread school closures triggered by COVID-19 have significantly increased the online activity of millions of children and adolescents globally. According to the Turkish Statistical Institute Household Information Technology Usage Survey, the use of information technologies between the ages of 6-15 increased from 50.8% in 2013 to 79% in 2020 and 82.6% in 2021 (TÜİK, 2021). This shows that a large segment of society is at risk of being a cyberbully or a victim of cyberbullying. Hendekci and colleagues have shown that the increase in the frequency of Internet use during the pandemic, the change in the purpose of Internet use, and the sharing of negative experiences with others negatively affected cyber victimization (Hendekci et al, 2023).

When we look at the cyberbullying studies in Turkey, it is limited to relatively densely populated cities that are developed in terms of economic, socio-cultural and other opportunities. This study was conducted in a small city located in Central Western Anatolia. Each region in Turkey has its own unique socio-economic structure and urban identity. This is one of the possible reasons why cyberbullying is seen at different rates in studies conducted in Turkey. Different results have been shown in different countries depending on the social structure of the city (Dujmic et al, 2019).

Although age, gender and duration of internet use are shown as effective factors on cyberbullying (Tsitsika et al, 2015; Peker, 2015; Aboujaoude et al, 2015; Pelfrey and Weber, 2013; Carter and Wilson, 2015), the effect of this factor in small cities is not well known. In this study, adolescents were evaluated by dividing them into age groups as high school and university students and by dividing them into gender.

This study was designed to determine the situation of cyberbullying, which has increased due to the rapid advancement of information and communication technologies and their widespread use due to current needs, in a small city located in Central Western Anatolia in Turkey after the COVID-19 pandemic. While the age factor was evaluated by taking students from high school and university into the study, gender and duration of stay on the internet were also evaluated. The results of this study are important in terms of seeing regional/urban differences in the evaluation of cyberbullying in Turkey.

2. METHOD

The study included data from 111 female and 89 male (n:200) volunteer students. 68 (34%) of the students were from high school and 132 (66%) from university. The 'Cyberbullying Scale' developed by Regan W. Stewart was used in the study (Stewart et al, 2014). The scale questions were made available to the volunteers via the web. This scale included two general questions asking participants to indicate which electronic mediums (e.g., text messaging, social media websites, etc.) they had been bullied through and which mediums they had used to bully others. These questions were followed by 14 items asking how often adolescents had experienced different forms of cyber victimization in the past few months (scale provided at the end). For these questions, adolescents rated each item using a 5-point Likert-type scale ranging from 0 (never) to 4 (always). The Total Score was calculated by summing the individual raw scores; higher scores are designed to imply that cyberbullying victimization experiences are more frequent.

The study was approved by Afyon Kocatepe University Social and Human Sciences Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Board (DECISION: 2024/164).

2.1. Data Analysis

In the study, descriptive statistics were calculated for qualitative data as number and percentage, for quantitative data as arithmetic mean and standard deviation values. In the evaluation of quantitative data, firstly, Shapiro-Wilk test was used to determine whether the data had a normal distribution. It was determined that the data did not show a normal distribution and Mann-Whitney U test was used in comparisons. In the evaluation of categorical data, Pearson Chi-Square test was used. The significance level was considered as $p=0.05$, and SPSS 20.0 package program was used in the evaluation of the data.

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3. RESULTS

53.5% (n = 107) of all participants reported that they were subjected to cyberbullying, while 34.5% (n = 69) reported that they were bullied. The distributions according to their educational status and gender are given in Table 1. According to this data, no difference was seen between girls and boys who were subjected to cyberbullying and between high school and university students. It was seen that male students committed cyberbullying more than female students ($p=0.000$), and high school students committed cyberbullying more than university students ($p=0.043$).

The average CBS Total Score for the entire sample was 7.95 (SD = 10.02). The means, standard deviations and score ranges for each criterion used in the study are given in Table 2. As seen in this table, statistically significant differences were seen both according to their gender and educational status. Specifically, males (M = 9.58, SD = 10.14) had significantly higher GIS total scores compared to females (M = 6.63, SD = 9.78), and high school students (M = 8.60, SD = 8.12) had significantly higher GIS total scores compared to university students (M = 7.61, SD = 10.89) ($p= 0.002$, $p=0.036$, respectively).

Figure 1 shows the distributions of female and male students regarding being disturbed by others on the Internet. It is seen that female students are most disturbed by social networking sites (such as Facebook) (35.2%), while male students are most disturbed during virtual games (64.2%).

Figure 2 also shows the distributions of high school and university students regarding being disturbed by others on the Internet. As can be seen in this table, both high school (41.0%) and university students (47.1%) are most disturbed during virtual games.

The rate of bullying among female students is low (17.1%) and they mostly use instant messages for this purpose (18.5%). It is seen that male students (71.7%) mostly bully during games in the virtual environment (Figure 3). Both high school (46.2%) and university students (36.8%) mostly bully during games in the virtual environment (Figure 4).

There is no statistically significant relationship between the time students spend on the internet and being exposed to cyberbullying and doing cyberbullying. While the minimum time spent on the internet by female and male students is 1 hour, the maximum time spent by female students is 12 hours and 15 hours by male

students. When examined according to their educational status, it is seen that the time spent on the internet by high school students is a minimum of 2 hours and a maximum of 15 hours, while the minimum time spent on the internet by university students is 1 hour and a maximum of 12 hours (Table 1).

Table 1: Cyberbullying distributions according to educational status and gender.

	n	Age (mean±SD)	Time Spent on The Internet (hour/day) (mean±SD) (min-max)	Exposed to Cyberbullying n(%)	Cyberbully n(%)	Exposed To Cyberbullying & Cyberbully n(%)
Total sample	200	20±2,9	5,10±2,34 (1-15)	107(%53.5)	69(%34.5)	57(%28.5)
Girls	111	20±2,9	5,12±2,08 (1-12)	54(%48.6)	19(%17.1)*	18(%16.2)*
Boys	89	19±2,9	5,07±2,62 (1-15)	53 (%59.6)	50(%56.2)*	39(%43.8)*
High school	68	16±1,1	5,09±2,77 (2-15)	39 (%57.4)	30(%44.1)**	23(%33.8)
University	132	21±1,7	5,10±2,09 (1-12)	68(%51.5)	39(%29.5)**	34(%25.8)

*p=0.000, **p=0.043

Table 2: Cyberbullying Scale

	n	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum
Total sample	200	7.95	10.02	0.0	56
Girls	111	6.63*	9.78	0.0	56
Boys	89	9.58*	10.14	0.0	56
High school	68	8.60**	8.12	0.0	35
University	132	7.61**	10.89	0.0	56

*p=0.002, **p=0.036

Figure 1: Distribution of environments where girls and boys are exposed to cyberbullying.

Figure 2: Distribution of environments where high school and university students are exposed to cyberbullying.

Figure 3: Distribution of environments where girls and boys commit cyberbullying

Figure 4: Distribution of environments where high school and university students commit cyberbullying

4. DISCUSSION

Due to the requirements of the age we live in (especially in the last fifteen/twenty years), developing information technologies have led to an increase in the use of internet-based communication resources and therefore to an increase in cyberbullying and victimization. The Covid-19 pandemic that engulfed the whole world in 2019 is also an important factor in this increase (Sorrentino et al, 2023; Jain et al, 2020). When we look at the literature, it is seen that the majority of the cyberbullying prevalence studies conducted in Turkey belong to the years before the Covid-19 pandemic. This study aimed to reveal the prevalence of cyberbullying among adolescents in Afyonkarahisar, a small city located in Central Western Anatolia after the pandemic.

When we look at the cyberbullying studies in Turkey, it is limited to relatively densely populated cities that are developed in terms of economic, socio-cultural and other opportunities. Each region in Turkey has its own socio-economic structure and urban identity. When we look at the literature, we cannot find any studies conducted on high school and university students in different geographical regions of the country and in cities with different socio-cultural structures. When evaluating the frequency of cyberbullying, it would be

correct to consider the 5 years before and 5 years after the Covid-19 outbreak, considering that the prevalence of information technologies and internet-based communication sources has increased rapidly in recent years. In 2018, 31% of 1752 middle and high school students who participated in the study from 20 different schools in Istanbul, the most cosmopolitan and largest city in the country, reported that they were exposed to cyberbullying (Duman and bridge, 2020). In a study conducted with the participation of 1141 volunteer high school students in six different schools in Ankara, another major city in the country, during the 2018-2019 academic year, 35.06% of the students reported that they had experienced cyber victimization (Tunca 2019). In a study conducted by Eyuboglu et al. in 2019 with 6202 students aged 11-18 in Eskişehir, a province with a high socio-cultural structure, the prevalence of cyberbullying among adolescents was found to be 17%; the prevalence of cyberbullying was found to be 10.4% (Eyuboglu et al, 2021) . In a survey conducted among high school students in Muş in 2015, 49.6% of the participants stated that they had experienced cyber victimization, while 34.1% stated that they were cyberbullies (Hesapcioglu and Ercan, 2017). In a study in which 401 students from different types of high schools in a district of Van province participated, it was shown that 109 (27.2%) of the participants were "Tending to Become a Cyberbully" and 339 (84.5%) were "Cyber Victims" (Karoğlu and Çılgın, 2020). In the study in which a total of 6,539 students studying in 10 different high schools in a district of Hatay province participated in the 2015-2016 academic year, 32.58% was determined for the cyber victimization dimension and 25.96% for the cyber bullying dimension (Özer and Şad, 2021). The results of the studies show that cyber bullying is more common in cities where socio-cultural activities are few. Since students spend most of their time on online activities due to the lack of cultural activities where they can socialize and spend time in these cities, their tendency to be exposed to cyber bullying and to engage in bullying behaviors increases. Afyonkarahisar, where our study was conducted, is also an Anatolian city with fewer socio-cultural activities. In our study, 57.4% of the high school students stated that they had been exposed to cyber bullying in the last few months, while 44.1% reported that they had committed cyber bullying. We attribute the possible reason for the higher rates of cyber bullying compared to other cities to the fact that the study was conducted after the Covid-19 outbreak. Due to the transition to distance education at many levels of education during the pandemic, the time students spend on computers and the internet has increased. It is inevitable that this situation will lead to an increase in the number and frequency of cyberbullying behaviors (Alsawalqa, 2021; Utemissova et al, 2021). There is no publication in the literature showing the prevalence of cyberbullying among high schools in our country after the pandemic.

Our study is the first in the country to evaluate high school and university students together in terms of cyberbullying after the Covid-19 outbreak. While no difference was observed between high school students and university students who were exposed to cyberbullying, it was observed that high school students committed more cyberbullying than university students. When we look at the studies conducted among university students before the Covid-19 outbreak, it was shown that 41.8% of the 10,763 students studying at the Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences of a university as of the fall semester of 2019-2020 were exposed to cyberbullying at least once in the last 6 months. In addition, a significant portion of the participants, 47%, stated that they had witnessed cyberbullying (Dursun et al, 2020). In a study conducted on medical school students in 2019, the rate of those who said they had been exposed to cyberbullying in the last 3 months was determined as 17.9% (Sezer, 2019). In a study conducted with undergraduate students studying at Yıldız Technical University in the 2016-2017 academic year, it was reported that nearly half of the students were exposed to cyberbullying (Tezer, 2017).

The study also examined the relationship between gender and exposure to cyberbullying. While exposure to cyberbullying did not differ statistically between male and female students, it was observed that male students committed more cyberbullying than female students. Different results are seen in the literature regarding the relationship between gender and cyberbullying. While there are studies that conclude that there is no significant difference in terms of exposure to cyberbullying according to gender (Yıldırım and Yazgan, 2022; Dursun et al, 2020; Akcan And Öztürk, 2020), there are many studies that conclude that involvement in cyberbullying varies significantly according to gender. In addition to studies showing that male students are more victims of cyberbullying than female students (Erbiçer, 2019; Kağan and Ciminli, 2016), it has also been shown that they engage in more cyberbullying (Pamuk and Bavlı, 2013; Yaman and Sönmez, 2015; Peker et al, 2012; Seyhan-Şahin and Ayaz-Alkaya, 2023). Unlike all these results, Akbaba and Eroğlu determined that female students are more victims than male students (Akbaba and Eroğlu, 2013). In a study involving high school students in Konya province in 2022, it was shown that both the level of cyberbullying and exposure in males was higher in males than in females (Boyar and Arslantaş, 2024).

While researchers who found a significant relationship between cyberbullying and gender evaluated the reasons for this, they found that the social conditions in which they live could also be effective. It was also emphasized that gender roles are important in the differentiation in the levels of cyberbullying in Turkey in favor of male students. This is because boys perceive violent and bullying behaviors as an indicator of masculinity, such as courage and strength (Çiftçi 2010). The participation of female students in cyberbullying can actually be interpreted as female students who cannot behave aggressively trying to 'compensate' for the pressure they experience by engaging in cyberbullying (Eroğlu and Peker, 2015). In addition, being able to hide their identities in the virtual environment can cause female students to exhibit more courageous behaviors.

It is widely seen in the literature that there is a positive relationship between internet usage time and cyberbullying behavior (Erdur-Baker and Kavrut, 2007; Özdemir and Akar, 2011; Peker, 2015; Mishna and Choo, 2012). This relationship could not be shown in our study. The time spent on the internet declared by the participants in the study corresponds to approximately one third of the time spent awake. Since the majority of the students spend a long time in the virtual environment, no correlation was observed between cyberbullying and usage time.

Although there is no gender difference in terms of exposure to cyberbullying, the platforms of exposure differ. While female students are most exposed to bullying on social networking sites (such as Facebook) (35.2%) and during instant messaging (33.3%), male students are most exposed to bullying during games in the virtual environment (64.2%) and in chat rooms (30.2%). When evaluated according to their educational status, it is seen that the platform where high school students and university students are most exposed to cyberbullying is the same. They are most exposed to bullying during games in the virtual environment (high school: 41%, university: 47%), while high school students are second in chat rooms (38.5%), and university students are exposed to bullying during text messages (26.5%). Female students who say they engage in cyberbullying say they most frequently use instant messaging (18.5%), while 71.7% of male students say they engage in bullying during games in the virtual environment. High school and university students are most frequently bullied during games in the virtual environment. These findings reveal that students, especially male students, come into contact with cyberbullying during virtual games. In small cities where social life is low, it is seen that young people's first choice for having fun and socializing is to participate in online games. When the "Cyberbullying Scale", which evaluates the frequency of cyberbullying, is examined, it is found that the score of male students is higher than the score of female students, and the score of high school students is higher than the score of university students. This shows that male students and high school students are more frequently exposed to cyberbullying. The time periods questioned in cyberbullying studies in the literature are quite variable. In some studies, participants were asked about their cyberbullying experiences in the last month (in some studies, in an academic year, and in some studies, in the last year. Frequency was not questioned in most of these studies. The lack of a standard method for revealing cyberbullying creates limitations in comparison with previous studies.

As a result, this study revealed the following results:

1. Approximately half of high school and university students (53.5%) in a small Anatolian city were exposed to cyberbullying
2. Male students tend to engage in cyberbullying more
3. Male students are exposed to cyberbullying at the same rate as female students
4. High school students are exposed to cyberbullying at a similar rate as university students
5. Students spend approximately one third of their waking hours in the virtual environment
6. Male students and high school students are exposed to cyberbullying more frequently

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APPENDICES

SURVEY FORM USED IN THE STUDY (Stewart 2014)

The following questions are about your life in the PAST FEW MONTHS. Please mark the best answer. You can mark more than one option.

1. Do other kids use any of the following to bully you? (Circle all that have happened to you) board about you

- Email
- Text messages/Twitter
- Picture messages
- Instant messaging
- Developed a mean website or message board about another kid
- Online video clips
- Social networking site (e.g., Facebook) Chatroom
- Virtual world (such as Second Life or the Sims)

2. Do you use any of the following to bully other kids? (Circle all that you have used to bully)

- Email
- Text messages/Twitter
- Picture messages
- Instant messaging
- Developed a mean website or message board about another kid
- Online video clips
- Social networking site (e.g., Facebook) Chatroom
- Virtual world (such as Second Life or the Sims)

	Never	Almost Never	Sometimes	Almost all the time	All the time
How often do you get online or text messages from another kid threatening to beat you up or hurt you physically?					
How often do other kids leave you out of online groups on purpose?					
How often does another kid say something mean to you (such as calling you names or making fun of you) in a text message or online?					
How often does a kid who is mad at you try to get back at you by not letting you be in their online group anymore?					
How often do you get text or online messages that make you afraid for your safety?					
How often does a kid tell lies about you in texts or online to make other kids not like you anymore?					
How often does another kid say online that they won't like you unless you do what they want you to do?					
How often does a kid try to keep others from liking you by texting or posting mean things about you?					
How often does another kid send you a message saying they will beat you up if you don't do what they want you to do?					
How often do you get in online fights?					
How often does another kid put you down online by sending or posting cruel gossip, rumors, or something else hurtful?					
How often does another kid pretend to be you and send or post something that damages your reputation or friendships?					
How often does another kid share your personal secrets or images online without your permission?					
How often have you had to ask an adult to help fix something bad that happened to you online (like a mean picture of you was posted, people called you names, someone threatened you)?					